

Comment on: The real normative dimension of Decrees Power Authority of the Presidential Office of the Russian Federation

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The motivation behind the current comment on is the Official Letter by the First Lady of the United States of America dating since 15.08.2025 sent to the President of the Russian Federation.

A reasonable manner, amongst others, on looking at the content of this letter, I think, is as highly relevant to the issue of the Decrees Power Authority of the Presidential Office of the Russian Federation regarding the rights of the children of policy-prisoners. Perhaps, there is reflected in mind policy-prisoners' amnesty.

If so, then, the issue is highly relevant to the Political Science, however the addressat is wrong. Why?

Despite a lack of concreteness and ambiguous in tackling the issue of the children's' rights within the territory of the Russian Federation, as well as owing to the fact that there has been written "...some children are forced to carry a quiet laughter..." and a single Presidential signature shall "... restore their melodic laughter..." a possible alternative is to adopt the view that the First Lady of the United States of America has reflected in mind a group of children of the so-called *policy-prisoners*.

There is a room for a discussion devoted to the normative dimension of the so-called executive power and its extension to public elected officials. In this case there is assumed the Presidential Office of the Russian Federation's ones and the control of the executives of the Russian Federation.

According to the liberal political theory and democracy and a rather intuitive practice of the democratic public administrations under "*executive power*" there is frequently understood a set of Institutions that have been actually legitimated in using of force in a given territory. There are the Police, Prison system and Army. The latter Institutions, therefore, enforce the rules governing the society as determined by the legislature [1]. It is regarded as a typical formulation of the state power within the framework of the classical liberal policy principles.

The social-policy system of the Russian Federation is often described as (Dual-Channel Institutional Designed) "President-Parliamentary" one [2], and the Presidential Office of the Russian Federation have been characterized as powerful in exercising executive power *via* Decrees. The Constitutional decree power is constitutionally determined within the framework of the Article 90 (1) of the Russian Federation Constitution [3,4]:

Article 90 (1): *The President of the Russian Federation shall issue edicts and regulations.*

Therefore, the Russian Federation Constitution provides the Presidential Office the power to enact decrees without any further special delegation of power.

However, to some domains connected with operation of the Criminal Code and Public Prosecution in the Russian Federation Constitution is standing legislation. For instance, consider Article 49 (1), Article 49 (3), Article 47 (2), and Article 129, respectively.

Particularly, Article 129 (1) states that:

Article 129 (1): ".....*The public prosecution system of the Russian Federation is the unified federal centralised system of authorities.....its organisation and order of work shall be determined by federal law.* "

Therefore, the order of work of the Public Prosecutors is determined on the base on the Federal Law, not on the base on the Presidential Office's Normative Decrees.

The issue of policy-prisoners is directly connected with operation of the Criminal Code within the territory of the Russian Federation and the policy is set by law, therein.

Presumably, it would be altered by Presidential Normative Decree as far as any policy which is set by law should be altered only by a law [5] and a Decree represents, in fact, law, which covers a broad spectrum of executive actions.

Particularly, the Normative Decrees might be setting novel Laws under already existing legislation. However, first, the Russian President does not have the right to bypass the Parliament or he is not unilateral. (Consider the hybrid-regime type of the French President-Parliamentarism model [6]. It is the same one.)

Second, the President may not issue a neither Normative Decree, nor Nonnormative ones or so-called Secret Decrees that contradict the Constitution or Federal Law. Because, according to the Article 4(2) of the Russian Federation Constitution both the Constitution and the Federal Laws have supremacy.

Article 4(2): *The Constitution of the Russian Federation and federal laws shall have supremacy on the entire territory of the Russian Federation.*

Thus, in the discussed case, if it is so, if a Normative Decree by the Presidential Office suspends the operation of the Criminal Code, then, there is suspended the operation of all Courts. The latter action; if any, would, in fact, mean an attempt at usurping power. Such act; if any, contradicts the Article 3(4) of the Russian Federation Constitution. It states:

Article 3(4): *Nobody may usurp power in the Russian Federation. The seizure of power or usurpation of State authority shall be prosecuted under federal law.*

Furthermore, the Court is independent of the executives. However, Article 47(2) of the Russian Federation Constitution determines some domains of the judicial power interpreting and applying the Criminal Code.

Article 47(2): *Any person accused of committing a crime shall have the right to have his (her) case examined by a court with the participation of a jury in the cases envisaged by federal law.*

In fact, the Federal Assembly or the State Duma exercise power of control over the executives within the territory of the Russian Federation.

To sum up, a Presidential Decree of amnesty of the so-called policy-prisoners; if any, contradicts the minimum six Constitutional Laws according to the Constitution of the Russian Federation (2020), *i.e.*, Article 3(4), Article 129(1), Article 47(2), Article 49 (1), Article 49 (3), and Article 4(2), respectively.

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